

Why do millions of people die, are amputated or invalidated by superbugs and not cured by phages ?

Because the wrong doctor-near-the-top has the wrong mission in the wrong paradigm !

The author : Christian Bois - PhD 2005 - has been an underground whistleblower up to 2018 when he became aware of the phage HealthGate (1) he describes here. Since then, he has written many articles - on line in French - and sent many alerts to elected people. In June 2019, he begins to write in English about phagotherapy.

The dead hand and the garden's hut paradigm

A paradigm is a general and coherent way to behave.

Imagine there is a superbug in the rosebush of my garden.

Imagine this resistant bacteria enters and "eats" the flesh of my hand.

Imagine the doctor says " *We must cut your dead hand* ".

Imagine what it is to be in that dead end.

Imagine I heard about phages, the superbug natural killers.

Imagine I go to the river downstream the wastewater treatment plant - where " best " phages are.

Imagine I pick up water and bring it to my garden's hut.

Imagine I filter the water - **containing phages** and may be bacterias.

Imagine I put the water into a [Doulton filter](#) invented in 1835 to have water with phages and *without bacterias*.

Imagine that I spray this curing water on my dead hand.

Imagine the phages kill the superbugs and **my disease is cured**.

Case 1 : **You can** imagine these twelve steps from a dead hand to a safe hand.

This means that it will be easy for you to understand the following incredible story of a factory paradigm where doctors-near-the-top let people die, be amputated, invalidated by superbugs.

Case 2 : **You can't** imagine these twelve steps = it's so simple to kill a superbug !

It means that you are "contaminated" by the factory paradigm, that you can't imagine that simple solutions exist and are not used.

So, you will need to read this article several times.

" Let them die ! "

In 2019, in USA, France and other countries *where the factory paradigm is dominant*, it is **forbidden to save a patient** using non-factory devices - phages from sewage,

for example.

When a field doctor asks to a doctor-near-the-top to be allowed to save a patient with phages from the sewage, the answer is : “ *Let the patient die !* ”

Of course, the answer is formulated in a technical-factory way : “ *The à la carte phagotherapy is not allowed !* ” (2)

Which means without any doubt : “ *Let the patient die !* ”

Who is the doctor-near-the-top ?

He/she is the one who writes : “ *Let the patient die !* ” or so.

He/she is a civil servant working in/for state authorities - [FDA](#), [ANSM](#), etc.

People-at-the-top define general politics - policy for curing people.

The job of a doctor-near-the-top is to translate general policy into terrain devices (hospitals, regulations, etc.)

The dominant paradigm

Most - if not all - doctors-near-the-top were educated, trained, hired, in the modern “ *factory paradigm* ”.

This paradigm i.e. “ general and coherent way to behave ” uses the **war** metaphor. Especially a chemical war metaphor.

Bugs are poisoned by factory produced antibiotics, by [antifungal](#) drugs, etc.

Keywords of the paradigm are “ *kill with poison* ” and “ *factory produced poisons* ”

Most diseases are considered separated from the patient’s body.

For example, cancer cells are fought by anticancer poisons even if the anticancer poison may *severely harm the patient*.

Idem for antibiotics, etc..

Could it be different ?

The state of the art of the factory paradigm is :

- either a poison exists

- or the patient is invited to be amputated or invalidated or die.

We don’t know what should be the resulting devices if :

- the general politics set by the top could be different

- the doctors-near-the-top could be of different profiles / paradigm

- other translations could be done

Of course, with a totally different paradigm, things could be different.

We consider here an other health paradigm that we call non-modern “ *garage paradigm* ”.

The thinking processes and behaviors in the two paradigms can be compared. (3)

Paradigm’s immune defenses

We observe that people within the factory paradigm are very defensive / aggressive

toward people within the garage paradigm.

These defensive / aggressive responses are called “ *immune responses* ” by researchers like Moscovici or Sloterdijk.

Having immune responses is somehow a “normal” behavior.

Coexistence of paradigms

It is the *responsibility of people-at-the top* to establish a balance between paradigms.

Especially when the dominant paradigm - factory paradigm - is **no more efficient**.

The factory paradigm is responsible of the failure of the antibiotics scenario.

The garage paradigm is the **necessary alternative** to save millions of people from superbugs.

To be more precise, shall we start from the story of bacteria.

Antibiotic : the venom of bacteria

Most bacteria need to protect their life and territory.

For that purpose, a bacteria B1 creates a poison against another bacteria B2.

This poison, sort of venom of bacteria, when collected, becomes an antibiotic drug.

In the factory paradigm, bacteria work for humans to produce venom / antibiotics that we know as “VA”.

The venom / poison is collected and prepared for human use.

There are about 14 kinds of venom / antibiotics that were “ domesticated ”.

Now there is no more financing to find new venom / antibiotics - Jim O’Neill’s report.

Superbug : the shielded bacteria

Bacteria B2 can develop a protection, a shield, toward the bacteria B1 venom / antibiotic VA1.

And as well, bacteria B2 can develop shields toward VA3, VA4 ... VA14.

In so doing, the bacteria B2 becomes a *superbug*.

No venom can affect a superbug.

In the patient file, the doctor writes : “ *therapeutic failure* ”.

The patient dies, is amputated or invalidated.

The doctor never writes “ *factory paradigm failure* ”.

We have seen that in the “ *garden’s hut paradigm* ” it is possible to **save a dead hand** with sewage phages.

Superbug : the fragile bacteria

The capacity of bacteria B2 to resist to venom/antibiotic VA3, VA4, etc. says nothing about its capacity to resist to :

- [antibiotic honey](#)

- [origan du Comtat](#) or similar essential oils compound

- lytic phages - natural bacteria killers

Generally, resistance/shield for one type of attack has no efficiency against another type of attack.

This means that a suberbug is, most of the time, a **fragile bacteria** when facing other therapies.

The problem is that doctors-near-the-top don't like to see bacterias as fragile, doctors-near-the-top *need to be warriors*.

When the chevalier loses his enemy

So, the matter seems to be very simple : when a bacteria is strong in front of antibiotics it can be killed by antibiotic honey, origan du Comtat or phages.

But these three therapies are within the *garage paradigm i.e. local, personalised therapy paradigm*.

It is necessary to move from “ *Let the patient die !* ” to “ *Let the patient cure with the devices of the garage approach !* ”.

This means different people with different mind set toward different practices called the garage paradigm.

For example, an effective essential oils compound - like origan du Comtat - may be very harmful to the liver of a patient, etc.

So the therapy can *only be personalized* i.e. be developed within the garage paradigm.

What is meant by “ paradigm change ” ?

Key-words of factory paradigm shift to key-words of garage paradigm.

There is no more a “ugly” bacteria to fight but a global health challenge.

There is no more factory devices but the local and individualized practice of the garage.

The doctor is no more facing alone the bad bug - bacteria, ignoring a passive patient ; there is a patient-doctor-phage collaboration.

Being part of the factory paradigm is a 4 step process.

First people are “ selected ” : kids who imagine their life as poison warriors against bugs can be doctors in the factory paradigm ; others can't.

Second, in school and university, warriors are conditioned for thinking **only** in the factory paradigm.

Third, warriors get jobs and missions within the factory paradigm.

Fourth, on the job training is done by factory people.

This is why these people cannot shift to the garage paradigm.

The need of new people as doctors-near-the-top

Installing the garage paradigm needs :

- train new generations
- identify doctors who are at the margins of the main stream paradigm i.e. already in the garage paradigm
- hire some in the [FDA](#), [ANSM](#), etc.

I stress this point : the chevalier of the factory paradigm is **totally lost** in the garage paradigm.

The actual doctor-near-the-top if afraid, scared by the garage paradigm.

The chevalier-doctor-near-the-top if **afraid, scared by antibiotic honey, origan du Comtat and phages**.

Identifying existing *garage paradigm doctors* and train new ones seems very simple.
(4)

When garage paradigm = bolchevik paradigm

At the turn of the thirties, Ioseb Jughashvili a.k.a. Stalin decided to develop phage culture and phagotherapy in his “ bolchevik empire ”.

In 1942, when Hitler’s army and Stalin’s army where in the field near Stalingrad an epidemic of cholera rose.

Stalin soldiers had no problem with cholera : they had phages available. (5)

Hitler’s soldiers died.

After theses events, for many Americans, there was a multiple paradigmatic offence :

- bolcheviks won
- garage paradigm phages won
- antibiotics were “ out ”

From 1930 onward, the production of clinical academic publications about phages is huge in Russia, Georgia, Poland, Romania, etc.

And laboratory research publications as well.

These publications were never translated to English.

Nevertheless, many Americans - researchers, etc. - write about these publications !!!

They never read the publications but write that their content is crap, bullshit, etc. (6)

On the other hand, see publication by McCallin & col., [article in Niboch](#), etc.

The right to lie

In documents published by too many doctors-near-the top, mediatic doctors, researchers, journalists, etc. it is “ as if ” exists a “ **right to lie** ” about lytic phages -

superbug killers -, organ du Comtat, therapeutic honey, etc.

A bunch of false information is taken out of the hat to *denigrate the therapies in the garage paradigm*.

There is a vicious circle :

- they say that academic publications coming from the garage paradigm are “ *not scientific* ” *i.e. don't talk the language of the factory paradigm*
- they don't even read them
- they denigrate
- they forbid the use of garage paradigm devices - phagotherapy, etc.
- no new clinical - near the patient - publications are made
- phagotherapy is said either “ not confirmed ” or dangerous

Thousands of years of phagotherapy

The use of natural waters - rivers or springs - for killing bacterias has been developed by the first chaman-healers a long, very long time ago.

One of the big lies of people in the factory paradigm is “*phagotherapy is new, we don't know much about it.*”

More recently, during about a century, in Russia and neighbouring countries, millions of liters of phage preparations have been produced and given to patients - on wound or intravenous forms, etc.

The knowledge is huge !

Who will decide the paradigm shift ?

There are more and more superbugs, there are more and more people who die, are amputated or invalidated.

There are more and more people who travel to Georgia, Poland, etc. and come back cured.

In their countries - America, Europe, etc. - they were told “ *we are going to amputate your hand, your leg, your eye, etc.*”

The miracle stories are published everywhere, in any kind of media.

A few people are allowed to be cured within the factory paradigm.

Because the factory paradigm cultivates a few types of phages - although there are thousands of phages types.

Nobody know why but only “ dying people ” are allowed to be saved.

Most cases are “ phages from the sewage ” cases.

Famous cases are Tom Paterson's in USA, Isabelle's in London, some in France, etc.

Each and every case is ***a spotlight on the thousands of people who are not cured*** within the factory paradigm.

Conclusion

The everyday life for doctors in front of patients with superbugs is :

“ Sir, you are a “ therapeutic impasse ” for the factory paradigm, we shall let you die, being amputated or invalidated ! ”

“ Thanks ! ”

Who will say “ Stop ! ” to this horror show ?

Notes and references

(1) [A “gate” is a “scandal”](#)

(2) Not only phages are forbidden.

[Antibiotic honey](#) can save hands, feet, noses, ears, etc. and doctors are not trained to use it.

[Origan du Comtat](#) or similar essential oils compound are unknown by doctors - who, anyway, say it's inefficient and dangerous !!!

Factory phages are allowed but they don't exist !

In the lab of [Graham Hatfull](#), there are more than 14 thousand different phages for thousands of different types of bacterias.

It is not possible for factories to produce thousands of different phages “ just in case ” a patient need them.

The growth of phages can be done only locally ; it's what we call the garage paradigm.

(3) Paradigms comparison

Modern “factory paradigm”	Non-modern “garage paradigm”
Main metaphor is the chevalier fighting the ugly with a happy end for the princess	Main metaphor is Don Quixote’s saga, Stendhal, Proust, Dostoïevsky’s “hesitations” - Girard
Factories are needed to save thousands of princesses even if drugs kill “some” princesses	Garage is the right set to cultivate phages - for example - for curing princesses without killing some
Researchers are ashamed and sad to use trial and error methods, bricolage methods	Researchers are proud and happy to use trial and error methods, bricolage methods
Academic publications never talk about “bricolage” but purify the reality of the laboratory life i.e. an academic publication = a fairy tale	Academic publications try to be honest with the reality of bricolage.
“ <i>Not saying the truth about ...</i> ” is paradigmatic	Truth is important.
The important is to produce “pure” results, not “true” results.	The important is to have a fine ratio between the state of the patient - in risk of dying, being amputated or invalidated - and the risk of the therapeutic device.
There is a vicious circle : “ <i>Let them die !</i> ”	There is a virtuous circle : alliance of the patient + the doctor + the phages

(4) The resistance of bacterias to antibiotics was known when the first antibiotic was discovered !!!

The development of an alternative should have begun immediately - **Alexander Fleming** 1928 ; without this alternative, millions of people have died, be amputated, be invalidated !!!

(5) Cholera had always been an inevitable companion of armies at war. For instance, during the Sevastopol campaign of 1854–1855, the Anglo–French troops lost 73,000 men in military operations and 18,000 due to cholera !

In 1942, in Stalingrad, Zinaida Ermolieva, the woman in charge of producing phages was ready for the challenge : saving both Red Army and civil population from cholera and other bacterias. [Science First Hand](#)

(6) A typical comment seen on line - not only by US citizens : “{This guy Steve who went to Tbilissi to save his knee & life } *had to leave the richest country in the world*

for treatment .. Cmon now with that fucking braggarts bullshit... let's get down to business and go directly to the Healing process Part now... shit!!..... America's always the number one ! Fuck outta here with that crap ! ”

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